

BLUEMISSION AA

Building a coordination hub to support the mission
implementation in the *Atlantic and Arctic Basin*

Waves of Change - A Community Mural for Ocean Restoration

This project has received funding from the European Union's
Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under
Grant Agreement number 101093962.

Document Information

Project Name	BlueMissionAA – Building a coordination hub to support the Mission implementation in the Atlantic and Arctic Basin
Grant Number	101093962
Milestone number	-
Report title	Waves of Change - A Community Mural for Ocean Restoration - Report
WP number	WP5
Milestone due date	-
Submission date	
Dissemination levels	N/A
Lead beneficiary	SPI – Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação
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Document history and changes

Version	Date	Author	Description
0.1	04/06/2025	Diana Sousa, Elisa Frias-Bulhosa	1 st Draft
0.2	06/06/2025	Valerie de Liedekerke	Review
0.3	09/07/2025	Diana Sousa, Elisa Frias-Bulhosa	Review
0.4	25/07/2025	Baiba Prūse	Review
1	25/09/2025	Diana Sousa	Final Review and Submission

Authors | NA

Publisher | NA

How to cite | NA

Supported by/In partnership with

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1. Introduction

Artistic expression offers a powerful means to communicate the urgency and emotional weight of environmental issues, serving as a bridge between scientific knowledge and public awareness. In the context of ocean degradation and climate change, art has the unique ability to translate complex ecological challenges into accessible and emotionally resonant forms. By engaging the senses and imagination, it can make abstract scientific data tangible, spark dialogue, and mobilise diverse audiences. When combined with community engagement and interdisciplinary collaboration, art becomes a catalyst for empathy, critical reflection, and collective action toward sustainable ocean stewardship.

Building on this potential, on June 1st, BlueMissionAA launched its 5th Citizen Engagement Campaign, with the event titled “*Waves of Change – A Community Mural for Ocean Restoration*”, as part of the Cork Harbour Festival, co-organised by BlueMissionAA, SPI, University College Cork (UCC), and the Transforming and Inspiring Aquatic Landscapes Through Art and Science (TIDAL Arts) project. In the scope of BlueMissionAA's task 5.2, dedicated to meaningful and productive engagement of citizens, the campaign was specifically designed to connect with the local and academic community and visitors through two central activities. The first was the unveiling of “*Into the Reef*”, a large-scale, moveable, immersive street art mural designed to raise awareness about marine ecosystems and inspire reflection on human-ocean relationships. The second was the recording of the BlueMissionAA podcast, aimed at deepening public engagement with marine science, citizen action, and policy perspectives. Together, these initiatives provided dynamic, participatory platforms to raise awareness, foster dialogue, and advocate for a more informed and engaged approach to ocean conservation.

Importantly, this event was also part of the European Maritime Day in My Country initiative, promoted by the European Commission. This initiative seeks to raise awareness of the importance of oceans and seas by engaging the general public, with a particular focus on young people through various activities including exhibitions, workshops, and community events. Since its inception in 2018, European Maritime Day in My Country has grown substantially, with the 2024 edition featuring 531 events across 27 countries, both in EU and outside the EU. Participation by the BlueMissionAA project in the 2025 edition marked the second consecutive year that an event from the project was officially approved within the European Maritime Day in My Country framework, underscoring its recognised contribution to public engagement and maritime awareness at both national and European levels.

2. Key Activities

The citizen campaign event centered on two main initiatives: the unveiling of the immersive “*Into the Reef*” mural, encouraging public engagement with ocean conservation, and the recording of the BlueMissionAA podcast, featuring expert discussions to deepen awareness and dialogue.

2.1 BlueMissionAA Mural

At the heart of the event was the unveiling of “*Into the Reef*”, a large-scale, movable, three-dimensional mural created by Italian-Brazilian street artist Neto Vettorello. Installed at the UCC Hub, the mural transformed the space into a vibrant, immersive representation of an underwater ecosystem, inviting viewers to step into the scene and engage with the complexity and beauty of marine life. Highlighting the project’s commitment to sustainability, the artist and BlueMissionAA had previously agreed to prioritise eco-friendly materials in the creation of the mural.

The artwork portrays the beauty, variety, and fragility of marine biodiversity. An Atlantic Ocean turtle swims in the centre of the mural, surrounded by fish, a blue shark, and colourful corals. The artist’s careful attention to detail is visible in the smooth shades of ocean blues, the delicate depiction of marine plants, and the expressive shapes of sea creatures. This invites viewers to take their time and explore. The use of colour, texture, and depth makes the mural feel lifelike and almost dreamlike, inspiring a sense of awe. When looking at the artwork and experiencing the ocean’s ambience through it, one might unintentionally begin to reflect on the human impact on this beautiful environment, prompting a desire to take action.

Figure 1. Inauguration of the “Into the Reef” mural at the UCC Hub (Photo credits: RUA Productions).

“Into the Reef” serves not only as a visually striking centrepiece but also as an educational and awareness-raising tool. By occupying a prominent public space within the university, the mural draws attention to ocean issues in an accessible and emotionally resonant way, engaging both the academic community and the broader public.

To further amplify its message and foster a deeper connection with the community, the visitors were encouraged to write personal messages, reflections, and commitments on the reverse side of the mural panels. These handwritten contributions turned the artwork into a living, collective statement of care, responsibility, and hope for ocean restoration.

This interactive approach successfully merged artistic creativity with community involvement and ocean science, making the mural a powerful tool for public engagement. By physically

inscribing their thoughts, visitors moved beyond passive observation, becoming active participants in a collective narrative of environmental consciousness and marine protection.

Figure 2. Visitors engaging with the mural by writing personal reflections and commitments on the reverse side of the panels (Photo credits: RUA Productions)

Looking ahead, the intention is to transport the mural to other locations and relevant public events, expanding its reach and impact. By travelling across different communities and contexts, “Into the Reef” will continue to spark conversations, build awareness, and strengthen the collective commitment to ocean conservation.

2.2 Podcast

In parallel with the mural inauguration, BlueMissionAA recorded its first podcast episode live at the event. Hosted by Baiba Prūse (from BlueMissionAA and UCC), the episode brought together a dynamic panel of six guests representing diverse backgrounds and expertise: David Whyte, Ed Sheldon, Soli Levi, John Armstrong, Jesse Petterson, and Neto Vettorello. Together, they engaged in a roundtable conversation on the ocean and environmental preservation, community participation, and the power of creative expression.

The podcast conversation focused on several key themes: the importance of community engagement in environmental solutions, the benefits of interdisciplinary collaboration, and how artistic projects - like the mural “Into the Reef” - can amplify citizen's messages and mobilise public action. The guests shared personal experiences and scientific insights, enriching the audience's understanding of both challenges and opportunities in ocean restoration.

By recording the podcast during the public event, BlueMissionAA extended its reach beyond attendees to a global audience, enabling ongoing education and engagement. The episode is part of a broader strategy to use digital media to sustain momentum and foster a vibrant community of ocean advocates.

The episode is available on the project's official [YouTube channel](#), making it accessible to diverse audiences and helping build a wider community of ocean advocates across Europe and beyond.

Table 1. Podcast Guest Overview

Name	Professional affiliation and role	Contribution to discussion
Neto Vettorello	Italian-Brazilian multidisciplinary artist /citizen	Citizen participation through public art
David Whyte	Senior Postdoctoral Researcher with University College Cork, Ireland	Research and support inclusive, participatory frameworks to engage coastal communities in the management, protection, and restoration of their ocean resources and ecosystems
Ed Sheldon	Marine citizen science volunteer	Conducts seagrass surveys around Tralee Bay in Kerry
Soli Levi	Doctoral Researcher in Marine Governance and Human-Ocean Relations at HIFMB	The relationship between marine governance and emotion, particularly focusing on a case of wild seaweed extraction in Ireland and the emotional tensions surrounding the history and governance of Irish waters.
John Amstrong	Environmental Educator at Fota Wildlife Park	Public engagement and education on biodiversity and marine environments
Jesse Petterson	Lecturer with the Radical Humanities Laboratory and School of the Human Environment (Department of Geography) at University College Cork, Ireland	More-than-human relations, environmental change, and science and technology, with a specific focus on biodiversity loss and oceanic degradation.

Figure 3. Live recording of the BlueMissionAA podcast episode during the mural inauguration event (Photo credits: RUA Productions)

3. Conclusions

The “Waves of Change – A Community Mural for Ocean Restoration” event, part of BlueMissionAA’s 5th Citizen Engagement Campaign, successfully demonstrated how artistic expression, ocean science communication, and citizen participation can converge to advance ocean literacy and inspire environmental action. By combining the emotional resonance of a public mural with the engaging communication of a podcast, the event created multiple entry points for diverse audiences to connect with the urgent issue of ocean restoration and preservation.

Contributing to BlueMissionAA's aim of increasing public participation and citizen engagement in ocean-related concerns, The "*Into the Reef*" mural emerged as both a compelling artistic installation and a participatory platform, offering viewers an immersive experience that encouraged personal reflection and collective action. The act of inviting the public to contribute handwritten messages on the back of the mural transformed it into a living testimony of shared environmental concern and hope. Its planned mobility will extend its educational and symbolic value to new audiences across locations and events.

Likewise, the podcast episode recorded during the event not only amplified expert perspectives but also highlighted the richness of interdisciplinary dialogue. By making this content available online, the BlueMissionAA project has ensured that the impact of the event continues beyond its physical and temporal boundaries, fostering long-term engagement and knowledge dissemination.

Framed within the broader context of the European Maritime Day in My Country initiative, this event reinforced BlueMissionAA's commitment to inclusive, creative, and science-informed public outreach. It reflects the project's dedication to empowering communities, raising awareness, and building collective momentum toward a more sustainable and resilient relationship with our ocean.

The success of this report reinforces the value of integrating culture, science, and public participation in future campaigns.

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